

TEACHER IN A 21ST CENTURY CLASSROOM

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Abstract

Teachers are the light bearers for the future generation. There is a massive role of teacher for overall development of students either in the past centuries or in the age of science and technology. In the 21st century the teachers' role in education has become more important. They have to take the lead role for the development of educational status of their students as well as for their holistic development too. This paper here has tried to highlight the role and importance of teachers in the 21st century. It has presented the concept of 21st century teacher and the skills required in him/her. Lastly the paper has presented the idea of the role and responsibility of teacher in the 21st century classroom.

Key Words: 21st Century teacher, teacher in the classroom

Introduction

John Adams describes the teacher as a “Maker of man”. He is the torch-bearer of race and guardian of the future of mankind. He is essentially a nation builder. He is the key man for the future of the child and mankind. He plays an important role in shaping and moulding the personality of the child. His/her personal qualities, educational qualifications, professional training and the place that he/she occupies in the school as well as in the community plays a vital role for his success in future course of action as remarked by the Secondary Education Commission (1952-1953). The 21st century needs essential skills for the teacher to work effectively in the class along with having up to date knowledge were underscored such as honest, efficient, diligent, good communicator and a lifelong learner who is willing to go extra mile.

Concept of the 21st Century Classroom:

It means to promote essential learning and innovation skills. In order to prepare the students for a more complex life and work environment a 21st century classroom must promote creativity, critical thinking, communication and collaboration. Presently, we

need at least seven skills for the 21st century classroom. These are:

- Rational thinking and problem solving tactics
- Collaboration across social circles and networks
- Leadership skills and influence
- Adaptability skills
- Efforts and Entrepreneurialism
- Effective interaction and conversational skills
- Examining and Manipulating information skills
- Curiosity and creativity

Delivering 21st Century Skills in Indian Classroom:

The 21st century teacher will be with pedagogy of skills are:

- Teaching and developing thinking skills. It is associated with higher order thinking skills.
- Encouraging collaboration with suitable technologies, effective communications, team skills, inter-disciplinary approach.
- Enabling technologies with collaborative mediums, digital tools.
- Assigning student with clear transparent goals and objectives, self and peer assessment, relevant tasks, timely and appropriate feedback.
- Developing problem solving using the real world problems, in context of learning.
- Teaching using project based learning with incorporating suitable technologies, collaboration, and inter-disciplinary approach.
- Developing the information fluency, media fluency, technological fluency.
- Encouraging reflection with self review and peer review.

Salient Features of a 21st Century Teacher:

The 21st Century teacher, as a communicator:

The 21st Century teacher, as a communicator, must be fluent in tools and technologies that enable communication and collaboration anywhere, anytime. They do not only know how to do communication, they also know how to facilitate, stimulate, control, moderate, and manage communication.

The 21st Century teacher, as a learner, must:

- Be lifelong learners;
- Continue to absorb experiences and knowledge;
- Endeavor to stay current
- Change and learn as the horizons and landscape changes.

The 21st Century teacher, as a visionary, must have rich imagination to:

- See the potential in, grasp, and manipulate the emerging tools and web technologies;
- Look at others' ideas and envisage how they would use these in their class;
- Looks across the disciplines and through the curricula and make links that reinforce and value learning in other areas; and
- Make other fields as leverage to reinforce their own teaching and the learning of their students.

The 21st Century teacher, as a leader:

- Leads by example by championing processes and modeling skills – walks the talk;
- Is an advocator, early adopter – a maverick;
- Set clear goals and objectives crucial to the success of a project.

The 21st Century teacher, as a model, should model:

- The behaviors that they expect from their students –

tolerance, acceptance, a wider view than just their curricula areas, global awareness, and reflection

- Reflective practice by monitoring and evaluating their teaching via blogs, twitter and other media where educators can look both inwards and outwards.

The 21st Century teacher, as a collaborator, must be able to:

- Leverage collaborative tools like LinkedIn, Ning, Blogger, Wikispaces, Bebo, MSN, My Space, Slide-share, Pinterest, Instagram and Facebook to enhance and captivate our learners
- Share, contribute, adapt and invest using these collaborative tools.

The 21st Century teacher, as a risk taker, must:

- Have a vision of what s/he wants and what the technology can achieve to be able to identify goals and facilitate learning
- Take risks and sometimes surrender to the students' knowledge and use the strengths of these digital natives to understand and navigate products and have students teach each other.

Characteristics of an effective teacher in the real classroom:

- possesses a good academic qualification,
- has a positive attitude towards teaching profession,
- has a democratic approach to take decisions,
- shows maximum sincerity in shouldering responsibilities,
- is a lifelong learner and continuously remains in touch with latest developments in learning,
- takes the experience of the students as the base for teaching,
- encourages maximum student participation and interaction among students,
- is emotionally adjusted,
- actively participates in all co curricular activities with the

students, and

- keeps contact with parents, visits homes and participates in community activities.

General Perception of the role of a teacher as a leader of group and facilitator of learning:

The modern educators assign a number of roles to be played by the teacher as a leader of group and facilitator of pupils' learning. He initiates, manages, directs, informs, explains, demonstrates, clarifies, receives, feeds back, diagnoses and provides remedial measures. All these functions have unique implications for his role as a leader of group. His leadership is concerned with providing stimulation, encouragement and guidance for facilitating pupils' learning. He may also exercise his leadership in and outside classroom situations. He adopts different appraisal techniques to improve his leadership qualities. The following are some of the functions of a teacher as class-room leader.

The teacher as a question-poser – The teacher asks questions to stimulate the abilities of the children to think creatively. The students get opportunity to speculate, guess and explore ideas. Questioning is an important tool for learning by the students.

Teacher as a Psychological weather maker –

The teacher has to create a democratic climate in the class-room. He has to develop rapport with the learners, has to motivate them and has to bring a psychological weather for communication. He should try to remove the barriers of communication.

Teacher as a model – The teacher acts as a model for the children. His ideas, attitudes towards life and values are sources of inspiration for young learners.

Teacher as a manager – The teacher is the manager of the whole learning situation. If he knows the past and present of a child, he can anticipate the future of the child. He manages and organizes all activities with the cooperation of students. He prepares the stage of action for the learners.

Teacher as a director and controller – The teacher plays the effective role in directing and controlling learning situations. At initial stages some kind of guidance is useful. The teacher's role as director and controller is concerned with manipulating the learning situations to enable the students to face such situations boldly. Problem situations require such role of the teacher.

Teacher as a member of a group of professionals – There is a group of teachers in each school. The classroom teacher as a member of this group has to acquire some experiences, ideas, values, attitudes, skills and knowledge from other teachers. The teachers as a group can have impact on the student community. The Science Teachers' Association has been doing very good work in improving the quality of science teaching as well as science teachers through seminars, workshops, conferences and publications.

Teacher as a community worker – The activities of the teacher are not restricted to only the four walls of the classroom or the compound of the school. He has a lot of works of undertake in the community. The school is a part of the community so also the school members. Their involvement in community activities will enrich the community life and will provide successful leadership for successful accomplishment of plans and programs. The teacher should work as a link between the school and the community.

Teacher as a Counselor – Each teacher during the course of his interaction with students, has to give some counseling, both to the parents and students. The teachers may take home visits as a part of their duties. The effectiveness of counseling depends on the role perception of the teacher.

Thus an effective teacher has to play various roles both in and out the school situation.

How to make his teaching Effective in the Classroom?

- Who is to teach? The teacher is to teach and he must know himself.
- Why to teach? He should never forget even for a moment the

aims of education.

- What to teach? He should not think school to be merely a place for study.
- Where to teach? He should understand the child fully, his interest, aptitude, ability, aim, etc.
- How to teach? He must use proper methods of teaching.
- What to teach? He must have the mastery over the Subject-matter.
- When to teach? He should develop motivation among the students so as to make the lesson effective.

Role of Teacher as a Manager in the Classroom:

I.K. Davies calls the teacher as a manager because he has to organize teaching activities first and then he has to perform these activities in the teaching process. He has described the four (4) major activities which he performs in four steps: Step-I: Planning, Step-II: Organizing, Step-III: Leading and Step-IV: Controlling system is prepared with the help of these steps. These steps include the following activities:

- Analysis of the whole system.
- Task Analysis.
- Entering behaviors the learner.
- Specification of knowledge, skills and attitudes of the students.
- Identifying the students' needs.
- Formulation of learning objectives.
- Organizing learning resources.
- Selecting appropriate teaching strategies.
- Encouraging and motivating students-activities.
- Evaluation of teaching system.
- Learning and teaching system.

- Observing the learning system.
- Modification in teaching learning system.
- Planning for the Criterion test.
- Construction of Criterion test.

Suggestive Measures for the 21st Century Teacher in the Classroom:

- Develop love for children and deal with them sympathetically
- Develop sense of dedication for his profession
- Must work whole heartedly
- Develop his own personality
- Develop a knowledge of psychology
- Should develop sociability
- Must take interest in the society he lives in
- A Creative Person
- Good Communicator
- Innovator
- Planned Organizer
- User of Technology
- Agent of Progressive Social Change
- Good Coordinator
- Teachers may attend in-service teachers training programs and continuous professional development programs. They may realize that it is an essential component of their professional career.
- More programs to improve the quality of the teachers in which their personality development is focused may be introduced.
- Mastery over the subject; ability to adjust and update skills according to changing times; keeping them updated with the

modern technology is the need of time.

- Competency is a combination of three things, namely, knowledge, skills and attitudes. Schools and teachers have to face numerous new changes rising from their internal and external environment. To enable the teachers keep abreast with the newly arising trends more continuous development programs may be introduced.

Conclusion:

The 21st century is the age of Science and Technology, so that every teacher can get adequate information on real classroom learning. As a teacher he or she applies his or her technique procedures, skills, attitude and knowledge for making an effective teaching learning environment in his or her profession as well as these all must be updated for developing their competency, performance and commitment in the areas of their subjects from time to time for the needs of present generation of school going children.

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